

ADHESIVE BONDING LAP SHEAR STRENGTH IMPROVEMENT OF CFR(PEEK) LAMINATES BY SURFACE MORPHOLOGY MODIFICATIONS

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Abstract

In this paper, an experimental study concerning the effect of surface morphology on mechanical properties of adhesive bonding behaviour of continuous carbon fibres reinforced PEEK was performed.

Surface morphology of PEEK composite was varied by sandblasting process. 3D morphological parameters were calculated from interferometry measurements. Surface wettability behaviour was studied by deposited sessile drop technique and the contact angle between solid surface and liquid was measured. Thus, a correlation between surface morphology and contact angle variation was discussed.

Adhesive bonding strength of system PEEK/Epoxy/PEEK was measured by standardised single lap shear test. A correlation between surface morphology and adhesive bonding strength was investigated. The pertinent morphological parameters issued from a special surface filtering linked to adhesive bonding strength were determined.

1 General introduction

Continuous carbon fibre reinforced polymers composites have successfully replaced aluminium alloys in many aeronautic parts due to their improved lightweight, fatigue and chemical resistance.

These parts must be joined together. Nowadays, several techniques are used in structural joining of these materials: adhesive bonding, bolting, riveting and welding. The adhesive bonding technique is an ideal process for assembling structural composites

parts. Indeed, this method offers many advantages such as a uniform stress distribution along the joint, no reduction in the strength due to notch sensitivity of composite materials, weight and cost reduction, compared with other joining techniques like bolting, riveting or welding.

PolyEtherEtherKetone PEEK is a high performance semi-crystalline thermoplastic. PEEK based composites are increasingly used in aeronautical industry due to their improved impact behavior and their recycling potentials compared to thermosetting polymers.

However, high performance of these materials results in a good chemical resistance and hence their surface interactions with environmental elements are difficult. Consequently, surface preparation and treatment of PEEK composites are necessary to improve the adhesive bonding strength [1].

Currently, several techniques of surface preparation for adhesive bonding are used. These methods can be classified in three main groups: mechanical treatments like paper abrasion and sandblasting, physical treatments as plasma and laser treatments and finally chemical treatments like solvent degreasing and chemical etching [2].

Low cost, environmental friendly and easy to implement methods make sandblasting treatment one of the competitive methods for preparing thermoplastic material surfaces before adhesive bonding [3].

The relationship between surface texture and adhesion is complex. In the purpose of optimising abrasive surface treatment processes, different mechanisms and their interactions need to be understood [4, 7]. Moreover, the adhesive bonding

technology uses a liquid adhesive in majority of cases. Therefore, it is meaningful to apprehend the wetting behaviour of treated surfaces [5, 6].

In this paper, the effect of surface morphology generated by sandblasting process on wettability behaviour and adhesive bonding joint strength of PEEK composite in single lap shear configuration was studied. The cross correlation between interface (substrate/adhesive) properties and adhesive bonding strength was discussed.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Continuous carbon fibres reinforced PEEK composite was used as substrates. This material was supplied and manufactured by AIRBUS®. Commonly, this composite is named PEEK/APC-2 and reinforced by high resistance carbon fibres designed by AS4. The composite is made from 16 plies of UD prepreg laminae manufactured by Cytec®, in a quasi-isotropic configuration. In the aim to investigate the effect of the first ply orientation, two layup sequences were investigated: [+45/0/-45/90/+45/0/-45/90]_s first ply oriented at 45° according to the loading axe and [90/+45/0/-45/90/+45/0/-45]_s first ply oriented at 90°.

Fig. 1. Optical micrograph showing the structural configuration of PEEK APC-2.

Structural adhesive was used in this study. It was a two parts epoxy based commercially named 9323 B/A supplied from 3M®. Adhesive preparation

protocol was as follows: mixing the two parts in the following proportions; for 100% in weight of the epoxy base 27% are added for the hardener part as indicated in the adhesive technical support. The curing process was an isotherm at 65 °C for 2 hours.

2.2. Thermal and thermo-mechanical characterization

The Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) analysis was carried out using the DSC STAR 01 module from METTLER TOLEDO with a 25°C to 400°C temperature range and a heating rate of 10°C/min. The glass transitions were determined at midpoint. In semi-crystalline polymers the degree of crystallinity is an important factor, since the mechanical behaviour of these materials is linked to the crystallinity degree [8]. The DSC thermo-grams showed that PEEK APC/2 is in its maximum crystallization level. In fact, the absence of an exothermic peak that characterizes cold crystallization is not observed during heating. The degree of crystallinity was calculated using the following relationship (Eq.1).

$$X_c = \frac{Q_m}{\Delta W Q_c} 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, X_c is The degree of crystallinity (%), Q_m is The melting enthalpy [$J.g^{-1}$], Q_c is the melting enthalpy for fully crystallized PEEK $Q_c=130 Jg^{-1}$ [9] and ΔW : the weight content of PEEK on the composite.

Rheological characteristics of materials were performed with the use of DMA50 0.1dB from METRAVIB on rectangular (20mm×2mm×1.5mm) specimens in the tension/compression mode at controlled alternating strain. The temperature range was 25°C to 380°C with a heating rate of 1°C/min and the frequency was 1 Hz.

Materials	Type of reinforcement	Fibre weight content $W_f(\%)$	DSC		DMA	
			Glass transition T_g (°C)	Degree of crystallinity X_c (%)	Young Modulus (GPa) 25°C, 1Hz	α relaxation temperature T_a (°C)
PEEK APC-2	Continuous carbon	70	168	38	28	175
Adhesive 9323 B/A	-	-	66	-	3	92

Table.1 Materials characteristics.

2.3. Abrasive surface sandblasting process of surface generation

The studied materials were subjected to dry sandblasting (particles projection) with varying experimental conditions (particles characteristics, time of projection, angle, etc.).

The schematic principle of sandblasting process is shown in Fig. 2. The following results were obtained for subsequent fixed operating conditions: ceramic jet nozzle of 8 mm diameter, applied air pressure 5 bars, the distance L between the nozzle and target L=80 mm, impact angle of 90°. The influence of process duration and abrasive particle sizes are examined.

Fig. 2. Schematic setup of sandblasting device

Projection time was varied from 5 seconds to 45 seconds in the objective to investigate the surface morphology evolution as a function of time for three different particle sizes (50µm, 110µm and 250µm).

Abrasive particles (commercially named corundum) are composed chemically with 98% of alumina (Al₂O₃) and have an irregular shape with abrasive angles.

After abrasive treatment all samples were cleaned ultrasonically with ethanol for 15min to eliminate any particles and dust present on surfaces before optical, SEM morphological characterizations and wettability tests.

2.4 Surface morphological measurements

In the aim to quantify surface morphological variation according to the sandblasting treatment conditions, the metrological device selected was with light optical interferometer (3D topometer),

offering a good compromise between measurement time and data quality.

The metrological device used is a non-contact 3D topometer: Wyko[®] NT9300[®] from Veeco[®]. Measurements were based on vertical scanning interferometry mode (*VSI*) [12].

This surface metrological technique allows calculating 3D and 2D morphological parameters which constitute a quantitative way to appraise topographical distinction produced by changing sandblasting conditions.

The most pertinent morphological parameters were selected according to the physical meaning of interactions between solid and liquid in contact, also allowing to the interface properties between the composite and adhesive.

2.5 Wettability measurement

The contact angles between the deposited liquid (distilled water) and composite (treated and untreated surfaces) were measured using a DSA30 apparatus from Kruss[®].

The principle of this technique is the measurement of the contact angle between the deposited liquid (3±0.1 µl) and the substrate surface by optical visualization of the droplet. The measurements were based on deposited sessile drop.

Fig 3 illustrates an example of contact angle measurement of untreated surface (a) and sandblasted surface (b).

Contact angle calculation is based on the following equation:

$$\theta_a = 2 \arctan\left(\frac{H}{D/2}\right) \quad (2)$$

where, H and D are represented in (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Liquid contact angle measurement.

In this study only the static contact angle was investigated. After depositing onto the substrate, the drop shape was recorded using a camera-video. The static contact angle was taken at 20 seconds after

distilled water drop deposition, corresponding to the thermodynamic equilibrium of the triple point of liquid, vapour and solid.

Tests were carried out in an ambient conditioned room ($T=22\pm 1$ °C, $RH +40\pm 5\%$).

2.6 Joint preparation and testing

Specimens for single-lap shear test were prepared with two samples of PEEK measuring 106 mm by 25 mm and 3 mm thick bonded along 12.5 mm according to the international standard ISO 4587:2003 (Fig. 4). The overlap joint and the adhesive thickness (200 ± 20 μm) were controlled. The single lap shear bond strength for each material and sandblasting conditions was measured by tension loading using a MTS Bionix (Model 370.02) axial/torsion tester equipped with a 25 kN load cell and a displacement sensor at room temperature (23 ± 1 °C) and at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min.

Fig. 4. Diagram of single lap shear specimens.

The apparent shear strength values (τ) were calculated according to the following relationship ($\tau_{\text{max}}=F/A$), where F is the load at failure (N) and A : represents the overlap shear area (mm^2).

Fig. 5. Tested first ply configuration and fibres orientation.

To determine the effect of the composite first ply orientation on the single lap shear strength, two first ply configurations were studied, 1st ply oriented at 45° and 90° according to loading direction as illustrated in Fig. 5.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Morphological characterization

Scanning electron microscopy was used as a qualitative technique to bring to light morphological variation according to sandblasting application and treatment conditions.

Fig. 6. SEM micrographics showing an example of surface morphologies of PEEK APC-2: untreated (a) and sandblasted with 250 μm average particle size during 10 seconds.

According to the SEM micrographics of untreated and sandblasted surfaces the result shows that the sandblasting process modifies considerably the surface morphology (cf. Fig. 6). Moreover, surface morphology generated by sandblasting process is complex and present a multi-scale character characterized by a macroscopic morphological anisotropy.

The observed morphological result is due to the composite manufacturing process. In fact, PEEK APC-2 composite is made from layup of unidirectional plies in a defined sequence, however the first ply constitutes heterogeneity in carbon

fibres distribution along surface plane, characterized by areas with high fibres density and others with low fibres density as shown in figure (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Optical microscopy showing the firsts plies of PEEK APC2/AS4, and the non-uniform distribution of fibres.

The specific surface morphology generated by sandblasting is due to the different mechanisms of material removal involved by particles projection in the two areas. In the case of high fibre density zones, material removal is governed by fibres presence and interface (matrix/fibres). Therefore, it is more difficult than in low fibre density zones, thus leading to more important hollows in the case of low fibres density areas. Furthermore, the presence of continuous fibres constitutes drainage for the removal of material, which induces an increase in surface anisotropy generated by surface treatment following fibres orientation.

With the purpose of quantifying surface morphological variations, evolution of roughness parameters was investigated. Sandblasting treatment is considered as a quasi-random process and modifies considerably the surface topography, as shown in Fig 6. Therefore, the surface morphology parameters depend on treatment conditions.

Surface morphological complexity observed by SEM analysis has been confirmed by interferometry measurements. The measured 3D topographies show that treated and untreated surfaces present a multi-scale character in terms of surface heights. Two different scales were identified: the first is linked to the macro-morphology and the second to the micromorphology as shown in Fig. 8.

From the point of view of surface functionalization for phenomenological applications of this paper

(wettability and mechanical strength of the adhesive bonding), it is necessary to conduct a surface morphological evaluation approach by discriminating the two scales. The most widely used method in surface metrology to separate the different scales: form, waviness (macro roughness) and micro-roughness is filtering.

Fig. 8. 3D topographies showing surface morphology of sandblasted PEEK/APC2 composites during 20 seconds with 50 μm average particle size.

Filtering operation consists in the separation of topographic surface components. These components are generally characterized by a frequency designated by the terms "roughness" and "waviness". The principle is to transform the real surface at the interesting level of characterization, by the use of filters according to the morphological information of the analysed area [10, 11].

Gaussian filter defined in the international standard ISO 16610-61 was applied to measured topographies PEEK APC2/AS4 in order to analyze the surface waviness and microroughness separately. Filter wavelength (cut-off) selected is $\lambda_c=0.08\text{mm}$.

The most pertinent 3D roughness parameters were calculated according to the three separated surfaces: total surfaces, waviness surface (macro morphology) and surface microroughness. Fig. 9 shows an example of morphological separation from the total surface.

Fig. 9. Morphological surface separation: a) raw surface, b) macro-morphology and c) micro-morphology.

The first morphological parameter investigated is surface anisotropy. In the case of these materials the sandblasting processes increase the morphological anisotropic character of treated surfaces. As a consequence, only 3D roughness parameters were calculated, considered more representative of surface morphology compared to 2D profile parameters.

Generally, in surface metrological characterisation, surface amplitude roughness parameters are used to describe surface morphology. From a great number of standardised amplitude parameters, anyone could be chosen due to the similar tendency. The most popular and classical amplitude parameter is (S_a) (μm): defined by international standard ISO 25178 and defined by the arithmetic average surface heights (Eq. 3) corresponding to R_a in 2D profile analysis, according to ISO 4287.

$$S_a = \frac{1}{L_1 L_2} \int \int_0^{L_1} \int_0^{L_2} |Z(x, y) - \bar{Z}| dx dy \quad (3)$$

L_1 and L_2 are the number of points along the axes (X, Y), Z (X, Y) represent the heights (X, Y) for each point of the surface.

The variation of the parameter S_a (μm) as a function of projection duration and particle sizes corresponding to three surfaces calculation is shown in Fig. 10.

The results show that the calculated (S_a) parameter from total and macro-morphology surfaces has the same tendency (Fig. 10.a and b).

(S_a) increased significantly according to the average particle size. However, the average particle size has no evident influence on the surface amplitude variation, (S_a) increases randomly. Moreover, the result indicates that the dispersion of measurements are high. It points out surface heterogeneity due to composite manufacturing process.

Fig. 10. Evolution of the parameter (S_a) as a function of projection time and particle sizes: a) rough surface, b) macro-roughness surface and c) surface micro roughness.

However, analysis of (S_a) evolution based on sandblasting process conditions, the surfaces of micro-roughness shows stability of the surface amplitude heights after a period of 5 seconds (Fig.10.c).

Furthermore, the increase of the average particle size results in an elevation in the surface micro-amplitude. This indicates that the micro roughness is more discriminant to morphological changes and gives particles size signature.

However, though the (S_a) parameter gives information about the "surface roughness level", it does not provide sufficient information about the surface morphology that can be correlated to the wettability or adhesive bonding strength measurements. In fact, as illustrated in Fig. 11 different surfaces may present a same or a similar (S_a) value, but different peak-valley values and relationships with (S_a) and peak-valley distances [13, 14, 15].

Fig. 11. Schematic comparison between two profiles which are characterized by a similar amplitude parameter but a different morphology.

Therefore, the other roughness parameters as a function of treatment conditions were studied.

One of the spatial parameters which can describe the surface morphology is the density of vertices (S_{ds}). The S_{ds} is defined in the European standard EUR 15178N. The latter is defined by the following equation:

$$S_{ds} = \frac{\text{Number of summits}}{\text{measured area}} \quad (4)$$

Peak is considered as summit if it is larger than its eight neighbouring peaks [16].

S_{ds} evolution as a function of treatment conditions for the three separate surfaces (raw, waviness and micro roughness) is shown in Fig. 12.

The results show that the density of summits calculated from macro-morphology surfaces is weak between 40 and 100 per unit area (Fig. 12.b). Furthermore, the density of summits after treatment is almost identical regardless of the average particle size or duration of treatment.

In the case of total and micro-roughness surfaces (Fig. 12 a and c), the evolution of the density of summits shows clearly the effect of the average particle size. And morphological stabilization is observed after 5 seconds whatever the average particle size. The use of fine particles leads to a higher summits density.

Fig. 12. Evolution of the parameter (S_{ds}) as a function of projection time and particle sizes: a) rough surface, b) macro-roughness surface and c) surface micro roughness.

However, the calculated summit density on the raw surfaces is greater than in the case of micro-roughness surfaces. This result indicates that some peaks were removed from the micro-roughness surface by the effect of filtering. However, deleted peaks can be considered as significant peaks. Therefore, it is preferable to analyse the density of summits directly on total surfaces. In addition, Nowicki (1985) [17] demonstrated that the amplitude parameters and spatial parameters are not correlated. Consequently, the generated waves (macro-morphology) have no influence on the significant peaks generated (micro-morphology).

According to the composite properties and adhesive joint optimisation the projection duration is a crucial condition. Surface amplitude depends on this parameter. However, the increase of projection

duration leads to more damage composite surface by fibres fractures as shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. SEM micrographic showing matrix and fibres damage after sandblasting during 10 seconds with 250 µm average particle size.

Consequently, for the adhesive bonding correlation to surface morphology only projection time of 5 seconds was selected and average particle sizes were varied (50, 110 and 250µm).

3.2 Wettability analysis

The measured apparent contact angle (θ_a) was plotted as a function of sandblasting process conditions (projection duration and average particle sizes).

Fig. 14. Measured contact angle evolution as a function of sandblasting conditions.

The results show that the measured contact angles increase with time projection to reach a quasi-steady state after a few seconds of processing time. Furthermore, the results show clearly that the average particle size affects the wetting behaviour. The use of large particles led to an increase in the apparent contact angle.

These results indicate that there is a correlation between the wetting behaviour and surface morphology generated by sandblasting.

Morphological analysis showed that the composite PEEK APC-2/AS4 has a complex morphological anisotropy and multi-scale before sandblasting whatever the processing conditions. The morphological separation by filtering in micro and macro surfaces has shown that morphological parameters calculated from surfaces micro-roughness reflect a significant change according to the average particle size with a morphological stability in projection time variation. This corresponds to measured contact angle variation (cf. Fig. 14). Consequently, the variation of apparent contact angle according to the surface morphology is more linked to the micro-roughness parameters. Therefore the correlation between contact angle and surface morphology is calculated from the micro-morphology topographies.

Two significant morphological parameters were selected: the first concerns surface amplitudes expressed by (S_a) and the second concerns density and distribution of surface peaks expressed by (S_{ds}).

Fig. 15. Measured contact angle evolution according to: (a) arithmetic average surface heights (S_a) and (b) Surface density of summits (S_{ds}).

Fig. 15 shows evolution of apparent contact angle (θ_a) as a function of (S_a) (a) and (S_{ds}) (b) calculated from micro-morphology topographies.

These figures show that the apparent contact angle is correlated with the surface height (in terms of S_a) and the density of peaks (in terms of S_{ds}).

When a droplet is deposited on the surface, the first contacts occur at the peak summits. If the summit density (S_{ds}) is low and the surface amplitude (S_a) is high, the droplet needs a high energy to spread from one summit to another, leading to an increased apparent contact angle. The larger summit constitutes a geometrical barrier to the spreading of the droplet [6, 18, 19].

According to the morphological analysis, it was found that the parameters presented separately do not provide sufficient morphological information of the surface. The parameter (S_a) provides information about the magnitude of surface but not about the distribution, population or peak shape. The (S_{ds}) provides information about the presence and population peaks on the surface but gives about information on the height of the peaks. Combination of the two parameters can explain the changes in apparent contact angle. Recently a new 3D morphological factor is proposed (S_r) [6] in order to have a better description of the surface morphology. This parameter takes into account the two components: an amplitude component (surface heights) and a spatial component (distribution and population of peaks) which well representing the surface morphology in three dimensions. The factor (S_r) is defined by the following equation:

$$S_r = \sqrt{S_a^2 * S_{ds}} \quad (5)$$

S_a and S_{ds} are calculated from micro-morphology surfaces.

Evolution of the apparent contact angle as a function of S_r is shown in Fig.16.

The result indicates that the factor (S_r) present a good correlation with the apparent contact angle variation in the case of treated surface as shown in Fig. 16. The (S_r) is more discriminant according to the contact angle changes.

Fig. 16. Measured contact angle (θ_a) evolution as a function of (S_r).

This phenomenon is observed for lot of materials based on PEEK studied recently [6]. Then, it can then be concluded that the contact angle variation is highly influenced by the surface roughness.

3.3 Adhesive bonding versus surface morphology

Single-lap shear tests were performed to investigate the evolution of the adhesive bonding strength according to the sandblasting surface treatment conditions.

The increase of projection duration leads to more damage of the composite surface (fibres fracture). Consequently, projection time of 5 seconds was selected. Nevertheless, the evolutions of the maximal lap shear strength at failure were investigated according to the average particle sizes and first ply orientation.

1st ply oriented at 90°

The maximum recorded shear strength was plotted as a function of the average particle size.

Fig. 17. Evolution of the maximum lap shear strength as a function of the average particle size for the PEEK-APC2, first ply oriented at 90 °.

The results show that the maximum lap shear strength increases significantly after sandblasting treatment (Fig.17). The increase is almost 100% in comparison with untreated surfaces. However, except in the case of untreated substrates, the maximum strength is almost equal, regardless of the treatment conditions. Indeed, it was noticed that for all treated materials the failure occurs in the substrate by first plies delamination as shown in the figure (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18. Surface morphological Fracture after single lap shear test 1st ply oriented at 90°. Sandblasted at 5 seconds with 50 microns average particle size. The scale bar corresponds to 2.5 mm.

Consequently, the correlation does not allow taking into account the surface morphology on the adhesive joint behaviour, but only the adhesion resistance between composite plies. It can be only concluded that the sandblasting treatment improves significantly the adhesive bonding strength of PEEK APC2 composite.

1st ply oriented at 45°

The results of the adhesive joint strength are shown in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19. Evolution of the maximum stress as a function of the average particle size for the PEEK-APC2, first ply oriented at 45°.

This figure clearly shows that -as in previous case- the surface treatment has a favourable effect on the maximum lap shear strength. Moreover, the average particle size of 50 μm has slight influence on the

adhesive strength. The failure in this case and for all treatment conditions occur in the adhesive joint and is characterised by a mixed failure (adhesive & cohesive).

As discussed above, the sandblasting treatment generates many changes in surface morphology as peaks and valleys which can be considered as location of mechanical inter-locking between substrates and adhesive. However, to better understand the mechanism of adhesion by the mechanical inter-locking, a correlation between lap shear strength and morphological parameters is required.

The results in Fig. 19 indicate that the lap shear strength decreases while increasing the average particle sizes. The increase of the average particle sizes results in the rise of the surface amplitude parameters as shown in the morphological analysis. Thereby, increasing (S_a) is a positive point for improvement of mechanical behaviour of the adhesive joint compared with untreated surfaces. Nevertheless, until it reaches an optimal value the mechanical behaviour of the adhesive joint declines. However, the surface amplitude is an important morphological parameter to be controlled but not the key parameter to well describe the mechanical joint properties according to surface morphology.

One of 3D morphological parameters which can be correlated to the adhesive bonding behaviour is the factor (S_r). In fact, Fig. 20 shows the evolution of (S_r) according to the maximum lap shear strength, the results illustrate that the decrease of (S_r) enhances the lap shear strength.

Fig. 20. Adhesive bonding strength and measured contact angle versus (S_r) factor.

As defined above the factor (S_r) is a combination between surface amplitude parameter (S_a) and spatial parameter density of summits (S_{ds}), the decrease of (S_r) results in the increase of the density of summits (S_{ds}).

In the case of the highest summit density the distance between peaks is small, which increases significantly the sites of adhesion between the adhesive and created peaks, and therefore amplifies the mechanical inter-locking as illustrated in Fig. 21.

Fig. 21. Wetting and mechanical inter-locking comparison between two different morphologies with different summits density; S_{ds} (a) > S_{ds} (b) scale not respected

However, these interpretations cannot be applied for the smoothest surfaces. In fact, the results show for the untreated surfaces in the case of the both composites the shear bond strength is poor while the density of summits is high. This is due to the lowest level of the roughness defined by the amplitude parameters (S_a). In this way if the (S_a) parameter is not in the optimal value the adhesion by mechanical inter-locking is limited.

On the other hand, another important surface property is the wettability behaviour. As shown in Fig.20 the decrease of the measured contact angle improves the adhesive bonding strength in the case of sandblasted surfaces. In fact, the adhesive has a tendency to wet the real surface area and goes through the cavities (cf. Fig.21). This phenomenon promotes the mechanical inter-locking and therefore enhances the adhesive bonding strength.

The 1st ply orientation according to the loading direction is an important parameter to be taking

account in joint conception. This property is expressed by surface anisotropy direction. In fact, in the case of untreated surfaces the configuration at 90° present the best mechanical behaviour of the joint compared to 45° configuration with a shear strength of 15.3 MPa to 11.5 MPa respectively.

4. Conclusion

The effect of surface morphology generated by sandblasting on the wetting properties and adhesive bonding behaviour of PEEK/APC2 was explored.

Surface morphological variation according to sandblasting process conditions (projection duration, particle size) was presented. Surface morphological characterisation was performed by using light white interferometry.

Surface morphological analyses disclosed that sandblasting process modifies considerably the surface topography in terms of 3D morphological parameters. The presence of continuous fibres on the surface leads to a complex morphology after sandblasting application.

In order to better understand the effect of surface morphology on wettability behaviour and adhesive bonding strength, surface morphological separation was applied by special filtering. The global measured surface was separated in two surfaces at different scales: macro-morphological and micro-morphological surfaces. Pertinent 3D morphological parameters were calculated for each separated surface and the pertinent parameters which mastered wettability and adhesive bonding strength were discussed.

It was observed that the parameters calculated from micro-roughness morphology are more discriminate according to surface treatment conditions. In this scale of analysis, it was showed that after 5 seconds of treatment roughness parameters have a tendency to stabilize whatever the particles size. One of the 3D morphological parameters which can describe the surface morphology is the S_{ds} density of summits.

Surface morphology has a significant influence on the wettability behaviour. It was observed that the droplet contact angle increases with the average particle sizes. The correlation between wettability

and surface morphology was done by the new factor (S_r).

The mechanical inter-locking plays a leader role in the enhancement of bond strength. However, the efficiency of this phenomenon is linked to the surface morphology and wettability. The suitable morphology can be defined as surface which has a maximum peaks until a level of the roughness and surface wetting remain satisfactory.

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